

Peak Sanctuary of Mt. Juktas

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Mt. Juktas is a large mountain in north-central Crete, 13 km south-west of Knossos. In the Bronze Age, a religious sanctuary sat atop its highest peak, Psili Korfi. Similar mountain-top shrines known as "peak sanctuaries" were visited by worshippers on elevated peaks across Minoan Crete, but Juktas seems to have been the central and perhaps most significant of these sites. It was most likely connected, religiously and later politically, with the palace and settlement of Knossos, and was an important part of the political and ritual environment of the wider Knossos valley.

Date Range: 2000 BCE - 1200 BCE

Region: The Peak Sanctuary of Juktas

Region tags: Greece, Crete

The Bronze Age peak-top sanctuary of Mt. Juktas, Crete.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Evans, Arthur J. 1921. *The Palace of Minos: A Comparative Account of the Successive Stages of the Early Cretan Civilization as Illustrated by the Discoveries at Knossos*, Volume I. London: Macmillan. (pages 154-159 for Juktas excavation)
- Source 2: Karetsoy, Alexandra. 1985. «Ιερό Κορυφής του Γιούχτα.» *Πρακτικά της εν Αθήναις Αρχαιολογικής Εταιρείας*: 286-293.
- Source 3: Karetsoy, Alexandra. 1981. "The Peak Sanctuary of Mt. Iuktas." In *Sanctuaries and Cults in the Aegean Bronze Age*, edited by R. Hägg and N. Marinatos, 137-153. *ActaAth*, 4°, 27. Stockholm: Svenska Institutet i Athen.

Notes: "Source 2" (Karetsoy 1980) is the last of ten annual reports published in 1974-81, 1984, and 1985 in *Πρακτικά της εν Αθήναις Αρχαιολογικής Εταιρείας* on the excavations conducted at Juktas. There was not enough room to include all of them here, but each one is by Alexandra Karetsoy and titled, "Ιερό Κορυφής του Γιούχτα."

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: N/A

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:
– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:
– Year range: 1909; 1974-1990

Notes: 1909: a preliminary excavation conducted by Arthur Evans on Juktas' highest peak, Psili Korfi 1974-1990: excavations conducted under the supervision of the Ephor St. Alexiou, funded by the Archaeological Society of Athens.

↳ Name of excavation
– Official or descriptive name: The peak sanctuary of Mt. Juktas

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation
– Mountain

Notes: The sanctuary is situated on the highest peak, Psili Korfi (811 m), of Mt. Juktas.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature
– Terracing

Notes: Three stepped terraces comprise the main part of the open-air sanctuary.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: Archanes lies 1.5 km east of Mt. Juktas, while the palace and town of Knossos lies 13 km north-east of the mountain.

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: The Knossos valley, along which both Mt. Juktas and the palace and site of Knossos are located, was undoubtedly a point of access during the Bronze Age, with routes connecting the north and south coasts of the island (i.e. Warren 2004). Sea travel was made accessible by the Knossian control of the port at Poros-Katsambas, and, at different times throughout its palatial history, may have controlled additional nearby harbours such as Amnisos.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: Archanes lies 1.5 km east of Mt. Juktas, while the palace and town of Knossos lies 13 km north-east of the mountain.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

Notes: A long stepped altar located on the west sides of Terraces I and II. It is constructed on top of deep fissures in the bedrock.

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: 4.70 m long, 0.50 m high (Karetsou 1981, 138)

– Yes

Notes: A Cyclopean wall, made of large blocks of grey limestone bedrock from the mountain, encloses the sanctuary. It has been given a variety of dates from different scholars, from MM IA to LM III, but during excavations, G. Rethemiotakis (1979, 30, pl. 76) discovered an MM III/LM I offering-table built into the wall.

- ↳ The structure has a definite shape
 - Other [specify]: perimeter: 735 m; width: 3 m; height: 3.5 m

- ↳ One single feature

- Other [specify]: natural chasm

Notes: A deep natural chasm found between Terrace I and Terrace II was excavated to a depth of 10.50 m, yet still the bottom has not been reached.

- ↳ A group of structures:

- Yes

Notes: Three stepped terraces comprise the main part of the open-air sanctuary.

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

- Yes

Notes: All three terraces were built at the end of the Old Palace Period (Middle Minoan I-II) or beginning of the New Palace Period (Middle Minoan III). Their construction seems to coincide with the foundation of the new palaces on Crete and the significant control of the Palace of Knossos. Prior to their construction, the peak was probably the open-air sanctuary of the Knossos valley, a role suggested by the votive material and MM IA sherds found in the fissures of bedrock all over the sanctuary.

- Yes

Notes: A series of rooms (5, possibly 6) in between Terrace II and III. Votive offerings, offering tables, and vessels found in these rooms suggest that the group served an auxiliary function in the worship at the shrine.

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

- Yes

- ↳ A group of features:

- No

- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

- Yes

Notes: The structures and features making up the physical environment of the Juktas peak sanctuary include three terraces, a series of auxiliary rooms (five or six room), a stepped altar, a deep natural chasm, multiple fissures in the bedrock, and a Cyclopean perimeter wall.

- ↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know.

Notes: The structure/spaces were presumably used to facilitate ritual activities performed at the peak sanctuary, but the exact nature of such activities is unknown. Evans (1921, 159ff; 1928, 761; 1935, 607) believed that the Juktas peak sanctuary was a place of worship, used for the veneration of a goddess ("oreia mitir" [Mountain Mother] or "potnia theron" [Lady of the Animals]). Karetsou (1981, 151-152) suggests that the archetypal connection between a mountain mother and a young male god is reflected in the peak sanctuary worship of this Minoan goddess and a young Zeus, whose birthplace and burial location have traditionally been associated with Crete. Offering tables and ceramic objects left at the sanctuary (anthropomorphic and zoomorphic figurines, pottery, etc.) suggest that rituals involving offering and dedication took place, but it is difficult to identify the activities with certainty due to the lack of textual evidence and the reliance on the prehistoric material remains.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– No

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is assumed that peak sanctuaries were places of worship, with ritual activities involving the dedication of votive offerings and pouring of libations, as well as possible feasts, drinking rituals, and sacrifices. These activities appear to have been directed at supernatural beings or deities, though the lack of textual evidence makes it difficult to draw conclusions about the characteristics of a Minoan pantheon. Iconography is similarly ambiguous. Indeed, it is very challenging to identify images of either rulers or deities in Bronze Age Aegean art more broadly (Davis 1995; Koehl 1995; Blakolmer 2019), though some strong possibilities do exist in the Neopalatial period on Crete (ex. Driessen 2015, 36). These candidates reveal some general iconographic patterns that seem to identify important people within scenes, including seated women, often enthroned on elevated platforms, and floating figures seemingly descending from the sky. Seated females, who look out over the scene and are sometimes approached by other human figures not elevated on platforms, perhaps represent rulers

rather than deities, but iconographic similarities between such scenes suggest a supernatural identity. The enthroned, for example, is often accompanied by animals, real or supernatural, as seen in a clay sealing from Knossos which Arthur Evans (Evans 1928, 761; Evans 1935, 607) interpreted as a representation of the "potnia theron" ("Lady of the Animals") who he believed was worshipped at Mt. Juktas. These representations, however, have yet to be found amongst peak sanctuary material assemblages; instead, the anthropomorphic figurines found at Juktas and other peak sanctuaries have no distinguishing divine characteristics, and are therefore more often interpreted as representations of worshippers dedicated at the sanctuary by human pilgrims, rather than those of the supernatural beings for whom they were offered.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The earliest ceramic sherds and votive material at the Juktas peak sanctuary date to MM IA, suggesting that ritual practices began in a peak-top, open-air sanctuary and gained formality throughout the Protopalatial Period. The monumentalization of Juktas' structures and the quality of the material deposited there in the Neopalatial period, however, corresponds with the construction of the new palace, suggesting that the sanctuary was under the control of the palace at Knossos. This pattern corresponds with constructions across Crete, as the network of peak sanctuary sites and their ritual activities became far more centralized, presumably falling under the control of Minoan ruling powers located at palatial centres across the island.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although no specific material (or textual) evidence exists to suggest that the peak sanctuary commemorates a supernatural being, a long-held tradition sees Mt. Juktas as the burial place of Zeus. Alexandra Karetsou (1981, 152-153) believes this later myth may have Minoan roots, connecting the mythical archetype of a "Mountain Mother" goddess and a young male consort to the possible prehistoric worship of a female mountain deity and a young male god on Crete, and specifically at Mt. Juktas.

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The stepped altar (4.70 m long, 0.50 m high) is perched right on the lip of the natural chasm in the bedrock.

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: The terraces and rooms east of Terrace II abut one another (see Karetsou 1981, fig. 4).

Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Field doesn't know

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Karetsou (1981, 145) notes that "the architectural remains for this period are monumental, when compared with the other contemporary peak sanctuaries which have been excavated," and include

the remains of a Cyclopean wall around the perimeter of the sanctuary and large terraces. These constructions may, however, be monumental only when compared to the built architecture atop other peak sanctuaries.

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 40

Notes: Approximately 40%. Much of the physical area of a peak sanctuary is left as bedrock.

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

Notes: The wall measures about 3 m wide and runs a perimeter of 735 m around the site, but creates an irregular shape that does not always follow close to the sanctuary (Karetsou 1981,151).

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 3.5

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 3.5

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

Notes: Karetsou (1981, 145) describes a "thin layer of whitish, hard-packed, kouskouras-type earth" on Terrace III, and notes that it may have been the same material described by Evans (1921, 158, fig. 114) as the flooring in Room B1.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– No

↳ Plaster
– No

↳ Wood
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

Notes: The Cyclopean wall is made of large blocks of grey limestone bedrock from the mountain itself.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– Yes

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: N/A

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials
– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: No human remains or funerary construction has ever been found in the sanctuary, but it is interesting to note that, according to myth, the tomb of Zeus is located on Mt. Juktas.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Given the lack of historical documents in the Bronze Age and the challenge of identifying a religious hierarchy or Minoan pantheon, it is unknown if a supreme high god existed in Bronze Age

Cretan traditions, or if it was worshipped at any particular site. Although Arthur Evans advocated for the

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Very little is known about the spiritual beliefs and ideologies of the inhabitants of prehistoric Crete.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Very little is known about the spiritual beliefs and ideologies of the inhabitants of prehistoric Crete.

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Very little is known about the spiritual beliefs and ideologies of the inhabitants of prehistoric Crete.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although the anthropomorphic terracotta figurines found at Juktas and other peak sanctuaries are more often interpreted as representations of the worshippers dedicated at the sanctuary to a deity or deities, it has been suggested that they may instead represent deities themselves. A specific cult statue, however, is not recognizable amongst the assemblage.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although animal sacrifices are known to have been conducted in Bronze Age Crete, it is not known if they were ever conducted at peak sanctuaries.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– No

Notes: The vast majority of the material offerings found at Juktas are not made of any sort of valuable material and are mostly terracotta, but a few exceptions have been found: a gold amulet uncovered in the area of the third terrace (Karetsou 1981, 147), and some bronze artifacts, including an embossed bronze sheet shaped like a bird (Karetsou 1981, fig. 26) and bronze double axes (Karetsou 1981, fig. 14).

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes, as ceramic vessels are commonly found at peak sanctuaries.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

Notes: Particularly in fissures in the bedrock.

↳ Other

- Other [specify]: In addition to pottery and ceramic figurines (anthropomorphic and zoomorphic), "votive limbs," stone libation tables, bronze and lead figurines, clay sealings, bronze double axes, amulets, and seal-stones have also been found at Juktas.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

- Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

- Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

- No

Notes: Scholars sometimes refer to peak sanctuary worshippers as "pilgrims" and their journeys up the mountains to the sanctuaries as "pilgrimages," but these terms are used in a regional sense and do not necessarily refer to long-range travel for the purpose of worship. Celine Murphy (2019) has recently found that terracotta materials from Cretan peak sanctuaries reflect local provenances, suggesting the local manufacture of these objects, rather than importation from distant travellers.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

- Field doesn't know

Notes: Ceramic sherds and ashy deposits atop some peak sanctuaries suggest that feasting, ritual eating, or sacrifices may have taken place at these sites, but no conclusive evidence exists or has yet been published for feasting at the Juktas sanctuary on Psili Korfim.

Are festivals present:

- Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

- Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not definitively known whether or not divination was practiced at Juktas or other peak sanctuaries due to the lack of written records and material evidence for this practice. This does not, however mean that it was never conducted at these sites.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

- Field doesn't know

Notes: The best evidence for healing practices at Juktas and other peak sanctuaries is the presence of terracotta "votive limbs" and other body parts alongside the anthropomorphic and zoomorphic figurines found deposited at these sites. Christine Morris and Alan Peatfield (2014, 54-63) suggest that the "anatomical offerings" found at Juktas, Petsofas, Atsipadhes, Traostalos, and Prinias fit into a broader healing dimension of peak sanctuary ritual. Conclusive evidence, however, is still unknown, and speculation about a healing aspect of Minoan religion rests on interpretations of material culture.

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
– Yes

Notes: The material evidence points to the practice of small-scale rituals at Juktas, including the dedication of offerings and libations, and possibly practices of feasting, drinking, and offering of sacrifices.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
– specify: Field doesn't know.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:
– specify: Field doesn't know.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
– Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Notes: Presumably no, as there is no evidence for such resource control at Juktas; however, if peak sanctuaries were centralized under the control of Minoan palatial elites in the Neopalatial period, it is possible that the sanctuaries played some role in land or resource control across the island. Perhaps Juktas, under the control of Knossos, was involved in the control of resources in the Knossos valley.

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Alexandra Karetsou. "The Peak Sanctuary of Mt. Iuktas.". (R. Hägg , N. Marinatos, Ed.), Sanctuaries and Cults in the Aegean Bronze Age. Stockholm: Svenska Institutet i Athen.. isbn: 9185086436.

Reference: Arthur Evans J.. The Palace of Minos: A Comparative Account of the Successive Stages of the Early Cretan Civilization as Illustrated by the Discoveries at Knossos.. London: Macmillan. p.154-159